

IMPROVING ACTIVITIES OF PREVENTION INSPECTORS TO PREVENT RECIDIVISM AMONG WOMEN BASED ON MODERN INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES

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Annotation: In this article, improvement of prevention inspectors' activities to prevent recidivism among women based on modern international experiences, modern international experiences, their study, implementation and transformation into national legislation based on national customs and traditions, the field is a new there are suggestions and recommendations for bringing to the stage and improving.

Key words: women's criminality, recidivism, crime prevention, crime and crime prevention, service activities of prevention inspector, implementation, transformation.

Belgian sociologist and criminologist A. Kettle, one of the founders of scientific statistics, tried to explain the laws of crime development and came to the conclusion that "propensity to commit crime depends on a person's age, gender, profession, level of education, season of the year, etc. He not only explained the differences in criminality between men and women by the difference in physical development of the sexes, but also explained the deviant behavior of women by being cut off from social life and entangled in family obligations. According to Kettle, the tendency to crime is stronger in men than in women, because women are more influenced by emotions, they have shame - modesty and modesty, and also their social dependence and loneliness. because of their presence, they will have less chance to commit crime; moreover, because of their physical weakness, they are women Kettle. When explaining the differences in crime between men and women, attention is usually paid to the social and biological causes of crime. The study of crime among women as an independent element of crime was founded in the second half of the 19th century, and this issue was first paid attention to by Lambert Adolphe Jacques Kettle (1796-1874) and Cesare Lombroso (1836-1909). Women are not always able to take advantage of situations that encourage them to commit crimes. Representatives of the anthropological school - CH. Lambrozo and his follower in Russia T. N. Tarnovskaya explain this phenomenon somewhat differently³. Ch. Lambrozo explained that the intensity of crime among women is lower than that of men, due to the uniqueness of the female body, female nature and its "biological deficiency" to a certain extent. Another of Lambroso's famous ideas is that the reason for women's aggression is the fact that their husbands are unfaithful to them. According to the results of research conducted by Lambrozo, it was found that 71 of the 80 women who were imprisoned for committing a crime committed the crime in this situation. In particular, such events are known in the world judicial practice, which in the above-mentioned case served to soften the sentence issued by women for crimes committed against a person on purpose.

He put forward the opinion that the social environment causes the emergence of criminal behavior, women's biological characteristics determine specific types of crimes or, in some cases, limit their quantitative indicators, and are not considered the reason for the commission of these crimes. At the same time, women are less mentally affected by various difficulties and problems in their lives we cannot take into account the fact that it is protected, says A. Kettle.

Homicide by women has always attracted the attention of criminologists, since it has long been established that the rate of homicide and other violent crimes committed by women is relatively high.

Based on the obtained data and comparative analysis, P. Tarnovskaya concluded that there are some differences in anthropological characteristics between criminal and non-criminal women, as well as between certain types of murderers. In his opinion, the skull was relatively poorly developed and small in size, "numerous anatomical cases of genetic disorders - dystrophies of the face, head, ears, teeth, and changes in the activity of sensory organs were visible. . Criminal women who are curious and capricious and morally weak, who do not know the difference between good and bad, and who are afflicted with mental and nervous diseases, are really a defective product of the weakened or changed life energy of the rising generation... These are from the first days of pregnancy are people who have developed incorrectly. P.N. Tarnovskaya made a thorough and detailed study of the personality and behavior of 160 murdered women, mostly living in the center of the European part of Russia. All crimes were anthropologically examined, and most of them were examined for their ability to see, hear, smell, taste, and feel pain. Information about the past life of these women and their families, including their profession, illnesses, character, inclinations and habits, as well as psychological information obtained during interviews with offenders, was collected.

When assessing the micro-social environment in which illegal behavior is formed, it is necessary to dwell on the differences between women in crime related to the permanent or temporary place of residence.

The criminal activity of women living in rural areas is much lower. Consequently, the range of crimes committed by them is quite narrow. In the village, there are crimes related to economic and service duties related to the employment of women and girls in the fields of trade and public catering, as well as robbery of other people's property. Researchers who have studied crime among women have already noted that the level of such crime in rural areas is much lower⁴.

This is explained, among other things, by the influence of factors in the social environment. In the city, the control of the immediate domestic environment over human behavior is much weaker, which, of course, makes it easier to commit illegal acts. The preservation of strong social ties in rural areas, compared to the city, serves as an element of social control and forces to reckon with general social-psychological interdependence. According to Yu. D. Bluvshstein, the fact that a person adjusts his behavior to the views of the people around him in rural conditions should be seen as an expression of conformism, i.e. intolerance, rather than consciousness. This explains the reason why the representative of the village population easily succumbs to harmful influences after losing contact with the environment he is used to. In the family environment, rural women also commit crimes against the person and theft, but such crimes are condemned by the public much more strongly than in the city. In addition, women who have committed crimes in rural areas and are sentenced to imprisonment often do not

return home after their release, but stay elsewhere, mostly in cities. Even in this specific law, a specific feature of the rural microenvironment with its own criteria is evident, and these criteria are a purely psychological obstacle for women belonging to the above category to return to their former place of residence. serves because strong social-beneficial ties in the place of residence are directly related to the length of the sentence served as deprivation of liberty. The negative skills and principles of behavior acquired in Bundy conditions, in women's understanding, are related to the previous lifestyle in freedom.

CONCLUSION

Through this article, we will give a criminological description of women's recidivism, show its specific features, reveal the identity of female criminals and the mechanism of its formation in certain social conditions, as well as one of the most complex problems of criminology is the prevention of offenses and the punishment of women who commit crimes. We tried to offer ways to solve the problem.

From this point of view, the urgency of preventing recidivism among women is explained by the following:

- alarming trends in the development of recidivism among women in recent years;
- the increasing negative impact of women's criminal behavior on society, on the spiritual and psychological environment in society, on individual institutions of society, especially on family relations;
- in the structure of criminality among women, prostitution is the leading crime, these criminal acts cause great material damage to the economic system of the state and the personal property of citizens,
- the need to establish consistent preventive work based on the specific reasons and conditions that motivate women to commit crimes,
- such as the low level of scientific study of the problems of recidivism among women, which has a negative impact on the organization of crime prevention among women.

The problems of prevention of drug addiction and alcoholism as factors that directly affect crime among women are closely related to sexual subjugation both at the level of a specific person and at the level of society as a whole.

In the graduation thesis, certain features and their essence were revealed, which are characteristic only of the crime among women, and therefore allow to distinguish it as a separate phenomenon from the structure of the crime. These properties can be determined not only in the study of objective manifestations of illegal behavior, but also in the assessment of the characteristics of women's criminal activity and the reasons that motivate it.

In our opinion, all criminal-legal decisions related to the problem of prostitution should be based on the possibility of a separate approach to the person of such women who commit crimes and to the persons engaged in the exploitation of prostitution. Such an approach, firstly, allows for a more comprehensive description of the above-mentioned persons from the point of view of providing evidence in criminal proceedings, and secondly, it is considered a necessary condition for taking into account the psychological characteristics of a person in the implementation of individual preventive measures.

The assessment of negative factors of criminogenic nature affecting crime among women is closely related to the analysis of factors affecting crime in general. Therefore, before starting to consider the specifics of the prevention of women's professional crime, first of all, it should be

noted that they are closely related to the general policy of combating crime, including crime among women, and measures to prevent criminal professionalism. need a tooth.

Prevention of women's professional crime should include taking into account the methods of committing crimes by professional women criminals, the personal characteristics of women criminals, and determining their criminogenic connections. When studying the specifics of the activities of professional female criminals, taking into account the aspects specific to them, including the high level of latency of such crimes, the use of victimological signs in the behavior of victims by female criminals, the behavior of female criminals during the investigation of a criminal case this, in turn, requires the development of appropriate tactics for carrying out special investigative actions and procedural actions with the participation of professional female criminals.

When developing measures to prevent recidivism among women, it is very important to take into account its regional features and to forecast it based on these features. This will increase the level of objectivity of crime prevention among women. When we talk about prevention of crime, including crime among women, we need to study the factors influencing the commission of crimes by women and women. we would like to draw attention to the problem of crime prevention.

Problem 1: The alarming trends in the development of crime among women in recent years, the negative impact of women's criminal behavior on society, on the spiritual and psychological environment in society, on individual institutions of society, especially on family relations, is increasing;

Suggestion: In order to prevent this problem, prevention inspectors should inform the parents, guardians, wives of young girls in schools, colleges, and higher education institutions about the negative influence of popular culture and the protection of young girls from negative moral and spiritual factors. It is advisable to intensify the propaganda work in cooperation with the Ministry of Youth and Sports and other necessary organizations, to widely implement the issue of holding responsible persons (parents, guardians) responsible for the negative actions of young girls.

Support the implementation of the approved set of measures to strengthen the mechanism of "family-neighborhood-educational institution" cooperation,

- assisting families in participating in the spiritual, moral, legal, aesthetic, physical and labor education of minors, in forming a healthy lifestyle in them,
- to provide employment to girls, improve their working conditions, learn trades, engage in home economics. Assistance in the implementation of programs for the development of entrepreneurship,
- factors that have a negative impact on the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in the neighborhood, in families and among young people (various crimes among women, suicide, prostitution, drug addiction, early marriage of underage girls to prevent and eliminate the occurrence of
- employment of girls released from penal institutions and minors returning from specialized educational institutions, helping them find their place in life. The assessment of negative factors of criminogenic nature affecting crime among women is closely related to the analysis of factors affecting crime in general. Therefore, before starting to consider the specifics of the prevention of women's professional crime, first of all, it should be noted that they are closely related to the

general policy of combating crime, including crime among women, and measures to prevent criminal professionalism. need a tooth Problem 2: The issue of women's employment is not being properly resolved.

Proposition 2: From the production specialization of each region to prepare women and girls for a short-term and high-quality profession, to develop effective programs for regional employment of women, and to encourage programs that have achieved the intended result.

Problem 3: The purpose of punishment in penal institutions is not to punish the offender, but to educate him, and as a result, the moral and spiritual condition of women cannot adapt to the environment in society.

Proposal 3: The commission of a crime by a spiritually mature and educated woman can be observed in very rare cases, so it is necessary to ensure the continuity of the development of the spiritual and educational level of women, to encourage and even punish women who have achieved sufficient results. also in enforcement institutions. For example, in Brazil, when convicts serving a sentence in penal institutions read one book in its entirety, their sentence is reduced by four days.

Problem 4: The low level of scientific study of the problems of recidivism among women, which has a negative impact on the organization of crime prevention among women

suggestion: It is desirable to identify effective methods of prevention inspectors to prevent recidivism crimes committed by women and with a high probability of committing, to provide adequate incentives and to widely apply these methods. In general crime, criminal behavior committed by women differs from that committed by men. For this reason, the nature and consequences of women's crime, the method of committing it and the use of criminal weapons in certain situations, the role of participation in the commission of a crime, the choice of a crime victim, and domestic living conditions, etc. will be visited and necessary recommendations will be given. In this case, criminological forecasting of crime among women is of great importance. The main task of criminological forecasting is to determine the factors influencing crime, i.e. negative factors that have a criminogenic nature, which influence crime among women. The evaluation provides for the prevention of women's professional crime, the ways in which professional women commit crimes, the personal characteristics of women criminals, and the determination of their criminogenic connections.

According to research, the criminal behavior of women in general crime is different from that of men. For this reason, the nature and consequences of women's crime, the method of committing it and the use of criminal weapons in certain situations, the role of participation in the commission of a crime, the choice of a crime victim, and domestic living conditions, etc. will be visited and necessary recommendations will be given.

The overall level of criminal activity of women will remain quite stable in the next decade. However, the spread of religious fanaticism and the ideas of terrorism in some regions of our country can affect the current situation as a stabilizing factor. These and other similar situations should be taken into account when making long-term forecasts.

In the field of criminological forecasting of crime among women, it is very important to implement specific measures aimed at improving the general efforts of the state and statistical reporting, legal, socio-economic, demographic and other statistical data. Although the field of criminological forecasting is almost undeveloped in Uzbekistan, its development is important for crime, including crime between women.

Would have gained great importance in the way of choosing countermeasures and increasing their effectiveness.

In conclusion, it should be said that flowers are not suitable for a woman's delicate hands, but goodness, not evil, for her heart. "He should be the face of our society. No regrets or lamentations from his tongue, let the gods fly, let them sing of happiness and joy. For this, prevention of women's violations of the law should become the task of all of us, not only law enforcement agencies or related organizations.

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